

Trump's mercantilism? Post-Cold War reshaping of the politics and Economy of India in South Asia

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Abstract

The current global shifts in the economic sphere, with the imposition of tariff duties by the USA on some countries, especially India in South Asia, can bring about a lot of changes in the international political economy. The dependency in trade and commerce in this neo-colonialist order is from both sides. It's actually a zero-sum game, which attracts the strong states towards weaker ones. This paper dives into certain important questions: Is it really going back towards the mercantilist approach of the state by adopting protectionist measures, or is it just a way to assert power in the post-Cold War period by impacting global supply chains? What are the impacts on the South Asian countries, especially India (domestically or internationally), as most of them are the suppliers of finished products to the USA?

The application of secondary tariffs on countries like India to stop them from importing Russian oil is one of the reasons given by the USA. This paper uses the current trends in growth of an economy, followed by political ideas behind it and how this decision can impact the major political decisions in future, such as bilateral meetings, trade agreements and deepening the structural inequality in the economy. How a country like India will react to it, if the tariff policy is not revised, can shatter the domestic market through demand and supply, and this will create greater problems for the people. This paper will also analyze whether India is truly an emerging power in the world and a major power in South Asia, or if this tariff policy has the capacity to take this title from it. Will this economic change have an impact on the regime or the political system of the country? How does the media is shaping this issue in the eyes of its people are the two points on which the conclusion and prospects are built? The economy doesn't operate in a vacuum: politics shape it, whether we talk about mercantilist theory, fall apart due to economic liberalism or capitalist ideas criticized by Marxian understanding.

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As Francis Fukuyama said *The End of History* on liberal ideology with the end of the Cold War, so is it really the end of history on liberal ideas, or is the world order evolving into something new? This is now a critical question to understand.

Keywords

Tariff Duties, Mercantilist, Secondary Tariffs, End of history, South Asia, Liberal Ideas

Mercantilism as an idea or period

Mercantilism, as an economic theory, was not propounded by any one thinker like capitalism by Adam Smith. It was an idea that got spread in Europe in the early 15th century. The definition carries differing views, but as per Eli F. Heckscher, Swedish free-trade proponent, mercantilism is the age that arrived between the Middle Ages and the laissez-faire system. In the book named "*Mercantilism*" by Eli F. Heckscher, volume I, where he talks about Mercantilism as a unifying mechanism, and in the beginning, economists like Smith and Keynes favoured the idea of the mercantilist economy. He wrote two volumes on this theory, and an evolution of thesis can be clearly seen in his work, but as per Heckscher, mercantilism was the "system of power", and to whom? No one but the state, because it's the state that was the custodian of wealth and bullion. It can be understood like this: initially, he defined mercantilism as a unifying system, then as a system of power, then balance of trade and how the mercantilist approach only talks about money yield. On the notion of political ideology, he defined a line of difference which made mercantilism different from liberalism, and that is that in the latter state, it is considered as a watchman, while in the former state, it is powerful to control the trade of the country. It's a period in the history of medieval Europe. With the onset of the capitalist idea, the mercantilist thesis faded away from the arena, and that's what happens when alternatives are given in forms of theory or system; they replace the preceding ones with new notions and understandings. But the alternative doesn't suggest that the previous doctrine was null or void. In fact, what the cycle suggests is the repetition of one or the other idea in a different forum or by different leaders. Heckscher was not the only thinker to speak on mercantilism; there are many. Here, the idea is how one can say that the mercantilist approach gets revised in Trump's vision or imposition of tariffs on most countries and especially India in South Asia. Many of the speculations suggest that it's the protectionist measure that Trump's government is taking by imposing an extra 25% tariff on Indian goods, and that's what mercantilism was all about: protection and accumulation of one's own wealth. But, it's also correct to say that it cannot only be a reason to say that Trump's idea is mercantilist. There are other reasons too which satisfy this understanding.

Reasons behind Trump's tariff policy

Donald Trump, the powerful yet criticised President of the USA, is not only criticised by non-Western forces but from within as well. The book named "*Fire and Fury, Inside the Trump White House*", written by *Michael Wolff*, an American journalist, is a satirical presentation of his policies and how he deals with matters in a Presidential address. As Machiavelli suggested, civic virtues are different from personal virtues; how one behaves in a public space matters more for a ruler than how one behaves in personal space. Hence, the idea is not to project his personal figure but to show the public image through the policies he adopted in the past and present. It's important because the USA behaves like a sole power in a polycentric world order. I wouldn't say the superpower because there are many states that can give competition to the USA in terms of currency, defence, foreign policy, trade rules, visa policies, climate issues, and so on. The policy decisions, if traced from 2017, his first presidential tenure, it can be stated that many decisions faced a lot of grim consequences, for instance, the withdrawal from the 2015 Paris agreement, a step back from the **UN Human Rights Council**, recognition of Jerusalem as Israel's capital and moving the US's embassy over there, etc. Despite being an ardent supporter of human rights, freedom, and democracy, the state has shown a decline in its way of articulation and working mechanisms.

Tariffs and sanctions are important tools that the USA has used tremendously to oppose or to stop the flow of money or resources from any country. The current imposition of tariffs on India in the name of a Russian penalty has created economic problems for the Indian state.

In 2018, Trump's administration-imposed tariffs on Chinese products, and based on this, one could analyse the reasons why the USA started a trade war with many emerging economies of the world. Then, it was also considered a protectionist measure taken by the USA towards other states. The reasons were as follows:

First is the **trade deficit problem** of the USA. Trade deficit and trade surplus are two contrasting terms. The former means higher imports than exports, and the latter means more exports than imports for any state. It depends on the savings and investment part of the country, but not exclusively on this parameter.

Second is the **role of the dollar**, it has both positive and negative impacts; a strong dollar means that foreigners have to pay more currency to buy USA products, making it expensive for them, while on the side of imports, the nationals have to pay less amount to buy their own products, which creates more

demand and encourage more imports into the country. When imposed tariffs allow Americans to buy domestic products, it allows other states to invest in their economy. This justification is used by Trump for the Indian tariffs policy so that in some products, they directly invest in America.

Third is to **protect one's own economy** from **gross national debt**. As described by the US Treasury of Fiscal data, "The national debt is the amount of money the federal government has borrowed to cover the outstanding balance of expenses incurred over time". Generally, any state faces a debt-like situation when spending is greater than revenue; the country will face a deficit, and with time, these deficits accumulate and form national debt. From 1924 to 2024, it has increased from \$370 billion to \$35.36 trillion³⁸. Trump had also made the point that taxing imported goods can reduce the debt by \$4 trillion. However, domestically, the economy could have a bad impact in terms of wage decline, in a way that the state can stop all trading agreements, which leads to a fall in demand for any particular good, creating a kind of wedge between production and demand, leading to many losing their jobs or a decline in wages. In the globalizing world, the imposition of tariffs not only damages the domestic economy but also international markets, which ultimately will lead to a decrease in the contribution of GDP internationally. The main reason used by Trump's government is that India is promoting the Russia-Ukraine war by importing oil from Russia. But is this really a reason? If analyzing the trade balances of the USA and Russia, the imports from Russia increased many fold from February to June, then started decreasing from July, and it was only in August that the USA imposed tariffs on Russian imports of oil. After the war started in February 2022 between Russia and Ukraine, a notable change happened as the figures of imports went down from thousands to hundreds, and within that, also the fluctuations were noticeable and due to this, the trade balance got reduced (negative figures)³⁹. According to U.S. Census Bureau and U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis data, the imports from Russia fell to \$2.50 billion in the first half of 2025 from \$14.14 billion four years earlier. U.S. goods and services trade with Russia totalled an estimated \$5.2 billion in 2024, down 25.8 per cent (\$1.8 billion) from 2023, according to the Office of the United States Trade Representative⁴⁰.

The imposition of tariffs should happen right after the start of the war. Why did the USA wait for three long years to force India economically? Keeping this aside, the Modi-Trump government share cordial ties with one another, so why has India been put under a different taxing slab except for other Asian nations (for whom it's only 20%)? The consequences of the draft future prospect, the Indian state has to look for the profit that it gets, whether by importing oil from Russia or by accepting US tariff

³⁸ <https://fiscaldata.treasury.gov/americas-finance-guide/national-debt/>

³⁹ <https://www.census.gov/foreign-trade/balance/c4621.html>

⁴⁰ <https://ustr.gov/countries-regions/europe-middle-east/russia-and-eurasia/russia>

imposition, which is again very unfair.

India: Counterargument

India, a South Asian country and said to be an emerging economy, has been under the US's eye since the 20th century. The tariff policy adopted by the USA doesn't surprise the nation much, but the aggressive implementation in the pharmaceutical sector is a noticeable act. Geopolitically, India can't come under the Global North, not because it doesn't lie, but simply because it's still a third-world country. *Mohammad Ayoob* rightly pointed out the **dependence-domination relationship** between the Third World and the rest of the world in his book "*The Third World Security Predicament*". It talks about the autonomy of political elites from external pressure. In the globalized era where the flow of economy, culture, and ideas is so rooted that one can't help but be affected by any policy. After the arrival of the Modi government in India, the ties between the two are so evident through political campaigning of elections, use of slogans, and counter-China's role in the Pacific region. The USA is also the fourth largest partner of defence to India after Russia, Israel and France. On the lines of Indian educated people migration to USA Trump imposed temporary ban on work visa so to boost his policy of employing Americans in America which is another measure to protect its economy and now after the announcement of tariff, another decision by him was the increment in the price of H1B visa from \$10,000 to \$100,000 – a hike which is not normal. The pharmaceutical industry was exempted from it, but a 100% tariff is levied on patented drugs, and if India wants to trade, then they have to set up a plant in the USA (manufactured in the US), which again costs India high in terms of capital, land, machinery, production, labour, etc. Experts say that it doesn't harm India in the short run, as the US accounts for 40 per cent of Indian pharmaceutical products, but the use of **Section 232 of the Trade Expansion Act of 1962** is harming the steel and aluminium industry, as it faces higher tariffs in the US. It's been said that the tariffs are more sectoral in nature rather than country-specific. On 23rd September 2025, the meeting of *External Affairs Minister S. Jaishankar* with the *US Secretary of State Marco Rubio* in New York was on positive lines. Parallel to this, Trump shifted his move from multilateralism to unilateralism and talked of India and China being responsible for the continuation of the Russia-Ukraine war in his 80th UNGA speech.

In terms of economic challenge to India, *Crisil* estimates that the textiles, gems and jewellery, seafood industry accounts for 25% exports to the US, which will be most affected by tariffs, MSMEs share 70% and the chemical sector, where MSMEs share 40% will also feel the blow of impact. But, on the positive side, New Delhi is looking to diversify its economy by including more trading partners whose borders are free for exports, for instance, **the European Free Trade Association (EFTA)**. *Second*, the cost of Indian goods will increase in the US market, which ultimately will lead to lesser demand for

Indian goods, and hence exports to the US will decline. In terms of investment, foreign investors will hesitate to invest in affected sectors, leading to less exposure of the Indian market abroad in some sectors. Market volatility (price fluctuations) will rise owing to the change in demand and supply patterns between the two countries.

Back in 2019, India was in a trade war with the USA when the capital refused to exempt the Indian steel industry from taxes. But what's now? Whether going into a trade war will be good or bad for India will be discussed later in this paper. The matter of concern is whether India is willing to focus on deepening its ties with EU nations and major countries across borders, and it's also a suggestion by experts.

Analysis

The stand taken by Mr. Trump in the wake of the Russia-Ukraine war cited towards the idea of protectionism and revival of mercantilism, in which countries were only focused upon the notion of accumulation of their own wealth and bullion (gold), and it defined the prosperity of any state, which was followed in early stages before capitalism. Now, the question which can come to mind is if it's a revival of the periodic cycle whereby again the world has to see mercantilism working in contrast with capitalism. The current observation says that in term of economic ideology, it creates contradiction between the two ideologies as mercantilism is more about protection and command of economy in the hands of state while capitalism is more about free market and less state intervention and as far as US's economy is concerned in contemporary times as it's an ardent supporter of liberal-capitalist economy but critically tariffs is about protection and closing of economy. And he said it clearly through his "**America first**" policy by hiking the price of the H1B visa so that only Americans can utilize its manpower. Another major reason for this is the proclamation of the idea that the US is still the sole power in the world by showing the dependency of emerging economies of the world on it, for example, China, India, Bangladesh (not an emerging but a supplier of cheap labour force and part of triangular economies). Almost 69 countries come under the umbrella of tariff policy, and within it, India faces a stark differentiation from other countries, i.e., 50%. Syria comes second in this with 41% and Switzerland comes third with 39%. Under the 30-40% tariff slab, around 7 countries come (Algeria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Iraq, Libya, Myanmar, Serbia, South Africa)⁴¹. As per my analysis, the **US dependency on the MENA** region is quite low in terms of percentage. In 2024, the U.S. total goods trade with the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) was an estimated \$141.7 billion, according to

⁴¹ TOI Business Desk. 2025. "Trump tariffs hit dozens of countries: Which are the most and least affected? Check if India makes it to either list." The Times of India. August 1.
https://www.google.com/amp/s/timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/international-business/trump-tariffs-hit-dozens-of-countries-which-are-the-most-and-least-affected-check-if-india-makes-it-to-either-list/amp_articleshow/123034197.cms

the Office of the United States Trade Representative⁴². However, the US's economy accounts for \$30 trillion, which means roughly it forms only 0.47 per cent of the US's economy. The trade balance which the USA shared with the MENA region was in surplus, which was \$19.1 billion as per the United States Trade Representative (USTR). MENA is known for oil and gas supplies, as the tariffs don't affect the economy directly, but they affect the exports of these supplies in the long run. But another reason could be the ongoing Israel-Hamas conflict, which is shattering the Middle Eastern region to a greater degree. The tariffs are more on Syria because of the recent conflict, which can be cited as an effort to hinder these economies, and the dependency factor applies here as well. It could be a major blow to the MENA region due to the Islamophobic notion of the USA, which was triggered in the 9/11 attacks, and somehow defines the past experiences of the state. The overall impact will also be felt in the US because it will become the reason for a rise in inflation. The projections are many and can't be depicted clearly due to a hazy picture.

Second, the point of contention is the relationship of Trump-Modi government as one can see the portrayal of their personalities in front of the world showed that the relation between the two are stable and friendly and the credit that Trump gave to himself for stopping the recent Indo-Pak war and his quest to get Noble peace prize, if India support it or not is another question of discussion. Furthermore, one can ask if these relations that India has with the US can save the economic plight in future. It can also be considered as a warning for India in the post-Cold War era, this tariff policy seeing whose side India will take: Russia or the USA. I would talk a little about NAM here. Previously, this policy prevented India from being involved in any power bloc, but the signing of the Treaty of Friendship by Indira Gandhi with the USSR created bitterness in India-US relations. India has to go back to its roots and revive NAM for the sake of maintaining cordial relations with these two blocs, as it's not in a position to be a part of any new cold war. The reason is very obvious, the USA will support Ukraine more than India because the opportunity cost for it is higher if it goes with India and why not with Ukraine, it wanted to be a part of NATO, which ultimately comes under the USA.

Third, the **impact on South Asia**, as the economy accounts for \$6 trillion and the Indian economy is \$4 trillion, which contributes to 80 per cent of this region. Hence, the impact can be seen in fewer jobs in the textile and pharmaceutical industries, which can lead to jobless growth in the region, too. Geopolitically, South Asia is a very important region not only economic but also political stakes are also high. For instance, the coldness in Indo-Pak relations is beneficial to the USA to some extent, and Pakistan has always been a supporter of US policy since the Cold War period. States like Nepal and Sri

⁴² <https://ustr.gov/countries-regions/europe-middle-east/middle-east/north-africa>

Lanka were always in the list of the CIA, and one of the reasons for conflict in these regions was mainly because of the capture of activists, political elites, young people, etc., which allows the US to intervene in the political decisions of South Asian states. On similar lines, sanctions and tariffs are tools to shatter the economy so when the economy is shattered, it will be later followed by political disorder in the state or region, and that's what the British did with India, they first captured the economy by setting up East India company and then captured it politically by exploiting the economy and understanding the administrative work.

Fourth, the change can be seen in the policy of the US in terms of the **rise in price of the H1B visa** right after the tariff policy and China's introduction of a new visa category named K-visa at the same time. It lowers the barriers for young people in the state for STEM purposes, and this takeover by China can counteract the US's actions and can reverse the effect of tariffs through migration of labour. After all these measured consequences, the probability of getting a different result in future is quite high. In fact, the global shifts after the arrival of this policy might differ to a large extent. The above analysis and interpretation are the result of arguments and counterarguments presented by both states in today's scenario; however, it doesn't have a clear picture or statistical data, but whatever data is present right now, from all these sources, this analysis is drawn. But the chances of both economies getting affected badly are high if this policy runs for a long time.

Conclusion

The paper presents the current status of Trump's tariff policy and analyses it, especially from the perspective of India. It provides the arguments provided by both countries. In the USA, it was in defence of why the taxation is high in India, and all the reasons for that are highlighted above. In contrast to this, the Indian counterargument is taken from the affected version as to how this policy will hinder the economic and political activities between states. And, in the analytical part, I have interpreted from a dual perspective and arrived at the above-mentioned results, which are not very accurate but predictable. Whatever happens on the global platform will definitely have regional and sub-regional impact, and sometimes the results are non-negotiable in nature. We have to see how global shifts will happen in the economic paradigm of these two states. India need to dig deep in this policy framework and take its decision based on the interest of its people not who are living despite the relations the country share with it and the state need to maintain its neutrality in world forums so to be on a safer side if the time of conflict may arise not because the country is not capable but because India has been a supporter of non-violent practices all over the world since the time of independence. The revival of NAM is the need of the hour at this point in time.

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